

**Triterpenoid and Related Compounds, Part-
XXIII : Triterpenoid Constituents of**

Alnus nepalensis* D. Don

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ALNUS nepalensis (Fam. Betulaceae) is a moderate sized tree available throughout the Himalayas from Kashmir eastwards to the Khasia Hills and is said to be of considerable medicinal value¹. A survey of literature revealed that no chemical work has been reported on it.

Petroleum ether extract of the bark of *Alnus nepalensis* collected from the Darjeeling district afforded β -sitosterol (0.05%) and 5 triterpenoids identified as lupeol (0.26%), betulin (0.23%), betulinic acid (0.21%), taraxerone (0.03%) and taraxerol (0.005%).

Experimental

Powdered trunk bark of *A. nepalensis* (1.7 kg) was exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The extract concentrate (32 g) was chromatographed over silica-gel (60-100 mesh), elution being carried out with petroleum ether and petroleum ether-ethyl acetate mixtures of increasing polarity, when the compounds described below were obtained in order of the elution. The identity of the compounds has been established from their physical properties (m.p., optical rotation, etc.) and in some cases through the preparation of derivatives.

Taraxerone (from petroleum ether eluate): $C_{30}H_{48}O$ (M^+ 424) m.p. 236° (petroleum ether-chloroform) (lit² m.p. 240°), $[\alpha]_D + 10^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.0974), $LiAlH_4$ reduction afforded taraxerol, m.p. 276°, $[\alpha]_D + 1^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.105°).

Lupeol (from petroleum ether eluate): $C_{30}H_{48}O$ (M^+ 424), m.p. 213° (chloroform-methanol) (lit² m.p. 215°), $[\alpha]_D + 24^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.0918), acetate, m.p. 217°-218°, $[\alpha]_D = +45^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.103°).

Taraxerol (from 1% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether): $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 426), m.p. 276° (petroleum ether chloroform) (lit² m.p. 280°), $[\alpha]_D + 1^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.1), acetate, m.p. 296° $[\alpha]_D + 7.2^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.105°).

Betulin (from 5% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether): $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$ (M^+ 442), m.p. 252° (absolute alcohol) (lit² m.p. 255°), $[\alpha]_D + 17^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.1), diacetate, m.p. 215°, $[\alpha]_D + 20^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.092°).

Betulinic acid (from 5% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether and more polar fractions): $C_{30}H_{48}O_3$ (M^+ 456), amorphous, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$ (C_6H_5OH , c 0.10) (lit² m.p. 320°), methyl ester, m.p. 222°, $[\alpha]_D + 7.5^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.099°).

β -*Sitosterol* (from 2% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether): white needles, m.p. 136°-137° (chloroform-methanol), (lit² m.p. 136°-137°), acetate, m.p. 126°.

References

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**Liquid-Liquid Extractive Separation of
Cobalt(II) with 2'-Hydroxy-4-Methoxy-5'-
Methylchalkone Oxime¹ (HMMCO)**

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2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime (HMMCO) has been used for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II)¹ and copper(II)². The stability constants and partition coefficients of extractable chelates have also been evaluated^{2,3}. It has been employed as indicator for titration of iron with EDTA and NTA^{4,5}. The quantitative separation of palladium(II), copper(II) and nickel(II) as oximates is also reported⁶.

The purpose of this paper is to establish the scope of application of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime (HMMCO) to solvent extraction of cobalt(II). The method proposed here is rapid, simple and affords separation and determination of cobalt at trace level.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions: 2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime (HMMCO) was synthesized and purified as reported earlier⁶. 0.001 M HMMCO in distilled benzene was used. The reagent was always stored in a refrigerator.

A stock solution of 0.01 M cobaltous sulphate was prepared in distilled water and standardised by known method⁷. The dilute solution of cobalt of desired concentration was prepared by appropriate dilution of stock solution.

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